

On generalized spiral-like pseudo starlike functions

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Abstract: This present work is to investigate the following properties namely: inclusion, integral representation, condition for univalence, coefficient inequalities and Fekete-Szego inequality of the class of function $f(0) = 0$, $f'(0) = 1$ define by Opoola differential operator denoted as $B_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$ via a functions of positive real part. Our results are accompanied with corollaries which satisfy some of the existing ones.

Key words: Opoola differential operator, Opoola integral operator, Spiral-like functions, Pseudo starlike functions.

1. Introduction

The concept of theory of geometry functions is an area of complex analysis which deals with geometric structure of analytic functions in the image domain and determines the geometric properties.

The study of normalized univalent function f of the form $f(0) = 0$, $f'(0) = 1$, in the unit disk $\mathbb{U} = \{\eta : |\eta| < 1\}$, has its beginning from the Basilevic map which was introduced in 1955 and define as follows

$$f(\eta) = \left[\frac{\alpha}{1 + \beta^2} \int_0^z [p(t) - i\beta] t^{-(1 + \frac{i\alpha\beta}{1 + \beta^2})} g(t)^{\left(\frac{\alpha}{1 + \beta^2}\right)} \right]. \quad (1)$$

where $p \in P$ refers to as functions with positive real part and $g(\eta) = \eta + b_2\eta^2 + \dots$ is starlike with the parameters $\alpha > 0$ and β are real and all powers mean principal determinations only.

The study of this Bazilevic map gave rise to introduction of many of its subclasses defined via both differential and interal operators by many researchers in the theory of geometric functions.(see [1],[2] [3] [4], [8], [9], [10], [11], [17], [25]).

The class of analytic function having a Taylor's series expansion has been normalized such its center is zero is define as follows:

Let $f(\eta) \in \mathbf{A}_j$ be class of the analytic function having the Taylors-maclaurin series of the form

$$f(\eta) = \eta + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} d_k \eta^k. \quad (2)$$

The author in [23], used the function of the equation (2) to introduced a subclass of \mathbf{A}_j refers to as Bazilevic functions of type β denoted by $B_1(\beta)$ for $\beta > 0$ satisfying the condition

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$$\Re \left\{ \frac{f(\eta)^{\beta-1} f'(\eta)}{\eta^\beta - 1} \right\} > 0.$$

Taking $\beta = 0$ the class $B_1(\beta)$ reduces to a starlike function satisfying the condition

$$\Re \left\{ \frac{\eta f'(\eta)}{f(\eta)} \right\} > 0$$

Also if $\beta = 1$, the $B_1(\beta)$ reduced to the class of bounded turning satisfying the inequality

$$\Re f'(\eta) > 0.$$

In [7], the class of β -pseudo starlike function was introduced where some of its properties were investigated and also studied in [26] define by the q -derivative. This was extended to the class of spiral-like functions in [24], where a new subclass was studied and referred to as spiral-like β - pseudo starlike functions and this subclass has been generalized by different operators (see [15]).

in [20], Opoola differential operator was defined as Let $f(z) \in \mathbf{A}_j$ such that $f : \mathbf{A}_j \rightarrow \mathbf{A}_j$. Then

$$\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{0, t} f(\eta) = f(\eta)$$

$$\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{1, t} f(\eta) = [1 + (\zeta - \mu - 1)t]f(\eta) - \eta t(\zeta - \mu) + \eta t f'(\eta) = (\Delta_t f(\eta)).$$

So that by mathematical inductions,

$$\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} f(\eta) = (\Delta_t f(\eta))(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n-1, t} f(\eta)).$$

Then

$$\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} f(\eta) = \eta + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [1 + (k + \zeta - \mu - 1)t]^n d_k \eta^k. \quad (3)$$

Equivalently, the novel Opoola's integral operator as defined in [16] is as follows:

$$\mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{0, t} f(\eta) = f(\eta).$$

$$\mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{1, t} f(\eta) = \frac{1}{t\eta^{(\frac{1}{t} + \zeta - \mu - 1)}} \int_0^\eta \eta^{(\frac{1}{t} + \zeta - \mu - 2)} [(t\zeta - t\mu)\eta + f(\eta)] d\eta = (I_t f(\eta))$$

So that by mathematical inductions,

$$\mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} f(\eta) = (I_t f(\eta))(\mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n-1, t} f(\eta)).$$

Then

$$\mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} f(\eta) = \eta + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{[1 + (k + \zeta - \mu - 1)t]^n} d_k \eta^k. \quad (4)$$

Therefore

$$\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} (\mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} f(\eta)) = \mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} (\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} f(\eta)) = f(\eta).$$

Clearly, varying the parameter n, t, ζ, μ , both Opoola's differential and integral operator reduced to Salagean differential operator, Salagean integral operator, Al-Oboudi differential operator, Al-Oboudi-Al-Qahtani integral operator, (see [5],[6],[21]).

In this study, a new class of spiral-like β -pseudo starlike functions is defined using the Opoola differential operator as follows:

Definition 1.1. For $n \in \mathbb{N}_0, \zeta, t \geq 0, \mu \in [0, \zeta], \beta > 0$, then $f(z) \in B_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$, if the following inequality holds,

$$\Re \left\{ e^{i\theta} \frac{\eta \left((\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} f(\eta))' \right)^\beta}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{n, t} f(\eta)} \right\} > \lambda \cos \theta, \eta \in \mathbb{U}, \quad (5)$$

where $\alpha \in [0, \pi/2), |\theta| < \frac{\pi}{2}$.

Remark 1.1. *i. $B_{\zeta, \mu}^{0, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$ reduces to class of spiral-like β -pseudo starlike functions.*

ii. $B_{\mu, \mu}^{1, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$ reduces to class of spiral-like β -pseudo starlike functions defined by Salagean differential operator.

iii. $B_{\mu, \mu}^{0, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$ reduces to class of spiral-like β -pseudo starlike functions defined by Al-Oboudi differential operator.

iv. $B_{\zeta, \mu}^{0, t}(\lambda, 0, \beta)$ reduces to class of β -pseudo starlike functions studied in [7].

2. Preliminary Lemmas

Let P_λ denote the class of the functions of the form

$$p(\eta) = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (1 - \lambda) \eta^k.$$

Then

$$\Re[p(\eta)] > \lambda \cos \theta, \lambda \in [0, 1), |\theta| < \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (6)$$

For $\lambda = 0$, we have the $p(z)$ which is a function having a positive real part, (see [7]).

Lemma 2.1. [7] *Let η be a complex number having positive real part, for any real number τ such that $\tau \in [0, 1]$, Re Then $\Re \eta^\tau \geq (\Re \eta)^\tau$*

Lemma 2.2. ([7] [13] [14])

Let $p \in P$ be the class of the function of the form

$$p(\eta) = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} p_k \eta^k, \eta \in \mathbb{U}, \quad (7)$$

where $p(0) = 1$ and $\Re p(\eta) > 0, \lambda \in [0, 1), |\theta| < \frac{\pi}{2}$. Then $|p_k| \leq 2$.

Lemma 2.3. ([7] [13] [14])

Let $p \in P_\lambda$, if

$$\Phi(\eta) = [p(\eta)]^\tau, \tau \in [0, 1].$$

Then $\Phi(0) = 1$ and $\Re[\Phi(\eta)] > (\lambda \cos \theta)^\tau$.

Lemma 2.4. ([7] [13] [14])

Let $p \in \mathcal{P}$, then for any real or complex number \mathcal{V} , we have sharp inequalities

$$\left| p_2 - \mathcal{V} \frac{p_1^2}{2} \right| \leq 2 \max\{1, |2 - \mathcal{V}|\}. \quad (8)$$

Lemma 2.5. [14]

Let $p(\eta)$ be holomorphic in \mathbb{U} with $p(0) = 1$. Suppose that

$$\Re \left(1 + \eta \frac{p'(\eta)}{p(\eta)} \right) > \frac{4\alpha\sigma + 8\alpha - p - 1}{4\alpha(\sigma + 1)}, \eta \in \mathbb{U}.$$

Then $\text{Rep}(\eta) > \alpha$, $\frac{1}{4} \leq \alpha < 1$, $0 < \sigma \leq 1$.

3. Main Results

Theorem 3.1. For $\beta \geq 1$, $|\theta| < \frac{\pi}{2}$, $\lambda \in [0, 1)$. Then $B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, n, t}(\lambda, \theta) \subset \mathring{B}_1(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}, \lambda^{1/\beta}, \cos^{1/\beta} \theta)$.

Proof. For $f \in B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, n, t}(\lambda, \theta)$, there exists $p \in P_\lambda$, such that

$$p(\eta) = e^{i\theta} \frac{\eta \left((\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))' \right)^\beta}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta)}. \quad (9)$$

So that, by simple calculation

$$[p(\eta)]^{\frac{1}{\beta}} = (e^{i\theta})^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \frac{\eta^{\frac{1}{\beta}} (\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'}{\left(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta) \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}}}.$$

By Lemma 1.4, we have

$$\Re \left((e^{i\theta})^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \frac{\eta^{\frac{1}{\beta}} (\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'}{\left(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta) \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}}} \right) > (\lambda \cos \theta)^{\frac{1}{\beta}}.$$

Let $\beta = 1 - \frac{1}{\beta}$, we have $f \in \mathring{B}_1(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}, \lambda^{1/\beta}, \cos^{1/\beta} \theta)$. □

Corollary 3.1. The class spiral-like pseudo starlike functions belong to $\mathring{B}_1(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}, \lambda^{1/\beta}, \cos^{1/\beta} \theta)$

Corollary 3.2. For $\theta = 0$, we have the class of pseudo starlike function defined by Opoola differential operator of order λ denoted as $B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, t}(\lambda, 0)$ belongs to $\mathring{B}_1(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}, \lambda^{1/\beta},)$

Corollary 3.3. For $n, \theta = 0, t = 1$ and $\zeta = \mu$, we have the class of pseudo starlike function defined by Salagean differential operator of order λ denoted as $B_{\mu,\mu}^{\circ,n,1}(\lambda, 0)$ belongs to $\mathring{B}_1(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}, \lambda^{1/\beta},)$

Corollary 3.4. For $n, \theta = 0, t$ and $\zeta = \mu$, we have the class of pseudo starlike function defined by Al-Oboudi differential operator of order λ denoted as $B_{\mu,\mu}^{\circ,n,t}(\lambda, 0)$ belongs to $\mathring{B}_1(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}, \lambda^{1/\beta},)$

Corollary 3.5. For $\theta = 0$ and $n = 0$, we have the class $B_{\zeta,\mu}^{\circ,t}(\lambda, 0)$ reduces to the class of pseudo starlike functions of order λ and belongs to $\mathring{B}_1(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}, \lambda^{1/\beta},)$ studied in [7]

Theorem 3.2. For $f \in B_{\zeta,\mu}^{\circ,n,t}(\lambda, \theta)$. Then f has the integral representation

$$f(z) = \mathbf{I}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},\sigma} \left[\int_0^\eta \frac{\beta - 1}{\beta} e^{-i\frac{\theta}{\beta}} \left(\frac{p(t)}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} dt \right]^{\frac{\beta}{\beta-1}}, \beta > 1, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{I}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},\sigma}$ is the novel Opoola integral operator.

Proof. Let $f \in B_{\zeta,\mu}^{\circ,n,t}(\lambda, \theta)$, there exists $p \in P_\lambda$, such that

$$[p(\eta)]^{\frac{1}{\beta}} = (e^{i\theta})^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \frac{\eta^{\frac{1}{\beta}} (\mathbf{D}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},t} f(\eta))'}{(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},t} f(\eta))^{\frac{1}{\beta}}}.$$

Then, let $\delta = 1 - \frac{1}{\beta}$, we have

$$[p(\eta)]^{1-\delta} = (e^{i\theta})^{1-\delta} \frac{\eta^{1-\delta} (\mathbf{D}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},t} f(\eta))'}{(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},t} f(\eta))^{1-\delta}},$$

so that

$$(e^{i\theta})^{\delta-1} [p(\eta)]^{1-\delta} \eta^{\delta-1} = \frac{(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},t} f(\eta))'}{(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},t} f(\eta))^{1-\delta}} \quad (11)$$

By simplifying (10) , we have

$$\mathbf{D}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},t} f(\eta) = \left[(e^{i\theta})^{\delta-1} \int_0^\eta \delta t^{\delta-1} (p(t))^{1-\delta} dt \right]^{\frac{1}{\delta}}, \quad (12)$$

replacing the value of δ and the anti-derivative of $\mathbf{D}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},\sigma}$ gives the result (10). \square

Corollary 3.6. If $\beta = 1$, the integral representation results to

$$f(z) = \mathbf{I}_{\zeta,\mu}^{\mathbf{n},t} \left(\exp \int_0^\eta e^{-i\theta} \frac{p(t)}{t} dt \right). \quad (13)$$

Corollary 3.7. *If $\beta = 1$ and $\theta = 0$, the integral representation results to*

$$f(z) = \mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} \left(\exp \int_0^\eta \frac{p(t)}{t} dt \right). \quad (14)$$

Corollary 3.8. *If $\beta = 2$ and $\theta = 0$, the integral representation results to*

$$f(z) = \mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \exp \int_0^\eta \left(\frac{p(t)}{t} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} dt \right)^2. \quad (15)$$

Corollary 3.9. *$f \in B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}}(\lambda, 0)$ reduces the anti-derivative to $\mathbf{I}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{t}}$ which yield the results in [7].*

Corollary 3.10. *$f \in B_{\mu, \mu}^{\circ, \mathbf{n}, 1}(\lambda, \theta)$ reduces the anti-derivative to $\mathbf{I}_{\mu, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, 1}$ which is the Salagean integral operator.*

Corollary 3.11. *$f \in B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}}(\lambda, \theta)$ reduces the anti-derivative to $\mathbf{I}_{\mu, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}}$ which is the Al-Oboudi-Al-Qahtani integral operator.*

Theorem 3.3. *Let $f \in \mathbf{A}$ and satisfy the condition*

$$\Re \left[e^{i\theta} \left(\beta \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))''}{(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'} - \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta)} \right) \right] > \frac{4\alpha\gamma + 8\alpha - 1 - 4\alpha(\gamma + 1)(1 + e^{i\theta})}{4\alpha(\gamma + 1)} \quad (16)$$

Then $f \in B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}}(\theta, \beta)$, for $\lambda \in [1/4, 1)$, $\gamma \in (0, 1]$ and $\beta \geq 1$.

Proof. Let

$$p(\eta) = e^{i\theta} \frac{\eta \left((\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))' \right)^\beta}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta)}$$

By logarithmic differentiation, we have

$$\frac{\eta p'(\eta)}{p(\eta)} = e^{i\theta} - e^{i\theta} \beta \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))''}{(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'} + e^{i\theta} \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta)} \quad (17)$$

From Lemma 1.5,

$$\Re \left\{ 1 + \frac{\eta p'(\eta)}{p(\eta)} \right\} = \Re \left\{ (1 + e^{i\theta}) + e^{i\theta} \left(\beta \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))''}{(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'} - \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta)} \right) \right\} > \frac{4\alpha\gamma + 8\alpha - p - 1}{4\alpha(\gamma + 1)}$$

By simple calculation, we obtain the condition (16). □

Corollary 3.12. *Varying the parameter n, σ, ζ, μ , different conditions of (16), will be deduced for class of functions $B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}}(\theta, \beta)$.*

Theorem 3.4. Let $f \in B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, n, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$. Then

$$|d_2| \leq \frac{2(e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)}{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 - \zeta - \mu)t]^n} \quad (18)$$

and

$$|d_3| \leq \frac{4(e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)}{[3\beta[1 + (2 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n - 1]} \max \left\{ 1; 1 + \left[\frac{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n 2\beta(\beta - 1)}{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n e^{i\theta}} p_1^2 \right] \right\} \quad (19)$$

Proof. Let $f \in B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, n, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$, then

$$e^{i\theta} \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta)} > \lambda \cos \theta \quad (20)$$

Equation (20), can be expressed as

$$\frac{e^{i\theta} \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta)} - \lambda \cos \theta}{e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta} = p(\eta) \quad (21)$$

so that

$$e^{i\theta} \frac{\eta(\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta))'}{\mathbf{D}_{\zeta, \mu}^{\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}} f(\eta)} = \lambda \cos \theta + (e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)p(\eta). \quad (22)$$

Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & e^{i\theta} \eta + 2e^{i\theta} \beta [(1 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n d_2 \eta^2 + [3\beta [(2 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n d_3 + 2\beta(\beta - 1)e^{i\theta} [(1 + \zeta - \mu)t]^{2n} d_2^2] \eta^3 + \dots \\ & = e^{i\theta} \eta + [(e^{i\theta} \eta - \lambda \cos \theta)p_1 + d_2] \eta^2 + [(e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)p_2 + (e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)p_1 d_2 + d_3] \eta^3 + \dots \end{aligned}$$

By comparing coefficient with respect to the power of η . Then

$$d_2 = \frac{(e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)}{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 - \zeta - \mu)t]^n} p_1 \quad (23)$$

and

$$d_3 = \frac{e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta}{[3\beta[1 + (2 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n - 1]e^{i\theta}} \left\{ p_2 - \left[\frac{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n 2\beta(\beta - 1)}{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n e^{i\theta}} p_1^2 \right] \right\} \quad (24)$$

By applying the Lemma 1.4 in (22) and Lemma 1.5 in (23), with simple computation, the inequalities (18), and (19) is obtained. \square

Corollary 3.13. Varying the values of the parameter $n, \sigma, \zeta, \mu, \theta, \lambda, \beta$, for the class of functions $B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\circ, n, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$, the inequality $|d_2|$ and $|d_3|$ can be deduce for classes such as spiral-like β -pseudo starlike functions, spiral-like starlike functions define by Salagean differential operator, Al-boudi differential operator and especially the β -pseudo starlike function (see [7])

Theorem 3.5. *Let $f \in B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\sigma, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$. Then*

$$|d_3 - \mathcal{V}d_2^2| \leq \frac{4(e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)}{[3\beta[1 + (2 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n - 1]} \max \left\{ 1; \left| 1 + \frac{(e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)}{2(\beta - 1)^2} \left[\frac{(2\beta - 1)[M + G\lambda]}{(3\beta - 1)[1 + (1 + \zeta - \mu)t^n]} \right] \right| \right\} \quad (25)$$

where

$$G = \beta + 2\mathcal{V} - [1 + (k - \zeta - \mu - 1)t]^{2n}$$

$$M = 2\beta^2 + (3\mathcal{V} - 4)\beta - \mathcal{V} + [1 + (k - \zeta - \mu - 1)t]^n$$

Proof. From equation (23) and (24), for any complex value \mathcal{V} , we have

$$d_3 - \mathcal{V}d_2^2 = \frac{e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta}{[3\beta[1 + (2 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n - 1]e^{i\theta}} \left\{ p_2 - \left[\frac{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n 2\beta(\beta - 1)}{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 + \zeta - \mu)t]^n} p_1^2 \right] \right\} -$$

$$\left[\frac{(e^{i\theta} - \lambda \cos \theta)}{(2\beta - 1)[1 + (1 - \zeta - \mu)t]^n p_1} \right]^2.$$

By Lemma 1.5 and simple computation, the inequality (25) is obtained. □

Corollary 3.14. *Varying the values of the parameter $n, \sigma, \zeta, \mu, \theta, \lambda, \beta$, for the class of functions $B_{\zeta, \mu}^{\sigma, t}(\lambda, \theta, \beta)$, the inequality $|d_3 - \mathcal{V}d_2^2|$ will be deduce for classes such as spiral-like β -pseudo starlike functions, spiral-like starlike functions define by Salagean differential operator, Al-boudi differential operator and especially the β -pseudo starlike function (see [7])*

4. Conclusion

The fact that the Opoola's differential operator generalized most of the existing operators give this study an interesting results accompanied with corollaries which certify the exiting results in the field of Geometry function theory.

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